

SHAPE MEMORY SANDWICH PANELS

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SUMMARY

Thermosetting resins and foams have been introduced which show elastic shape memory properties. Preliminary efforts to develop sandwich panels based on shape memory resin and foam core are discussed. Results show that deformations can be enhanced through the incorporation of plies on the compression surface which use a non-shape memory resin matrix.

Keywords: Elastic Memory Composites, Shape Memory Composites

INTRODUCTION

The current research was initiated to better understand the potential for a structural sandwich panel which could demonstrate rigid flexural properties, but under controlled conditions be readily deformed to an alternative geometry. Once in this alternate geometry the goal was to once again realize the flexural stiffness expected of a typical sandwich panel. To achieve this goal, a thermosetting resin and foam were employed which are based on shape memory polymers.

Shape Memory Resins

Shape memory thermosetting polymers enable fiber reinforced composites to be created which have the ability to be cured to shape and then deformed, frozen into an alternate shape, used in this altered shape, and returned to the original, as-cured geometry, as required. This behavior comes from a thermoset polymer that is capable of existing in two different phases, much like the martensite–austenite phases found in shape memory metallic alloys [1,2]. The polymer is able to undergo a large change in modulus, commonly a reduction approaching two orders of magnitude, as the glass transition temperature (T_g) is surpassed [2]. At this temperature, relatively large recoverable strains of the polymer matrix material are possible, and significantly less force is necessary to deform the composite. To restore the composite to its original as-cured shape, the temperature is again raised and the unconstrained shape memory polymer matrix composite recovers the original shape. This behavior has been the focus of a number of articles on viscoelastic modeling [3], which use a friction element to explain the behavior of the polymer.

Reinforcing fibers in a shape memory resin matrix composite can be utilized to increase the force of the recovery effect [1]. Thin shape memory laminates have been demonstrated in a number of applications, including as a mechanism for satellite

deployables [4]. In many ways, the shape memory resin performs like standard epoxy resins. Room temperature modulus is somewhat lower than a common high performance epoxy, and density is comparable [2]. Methods of composites manufacture, using the shape memory resins, are also analogous to approaches used with standard epoxy resins. Both wet layup and prepreg construction are possible.

Shape Memory Foam

Operating in a similar fashion to the shape memory resin, shape memory structural foam is also utilized in this study. This foam is used in place of a conventional structural foam, or honeycomb, core to enable large deformations of the sandwich panel structure. Using shape memory foam core, both large deformation displacements at elevated temperature, and high bending stiffness at room temperature, are possible [5]. The current shape memory foam core is created through foaming existing shape memory resins, which enables the tailoring, and matching, of the glass transition temperatures of the core and matrix material. The foam used is in the early research stages of development, and as such is denser than conventional structural foam core materials. Measured densities range from 20 – 25% of the resin density versus densities closer to 10% of the resin density for conventional structural foams. This shape memory foam also differs from most conventional structural foam cores in that it is of open-cell architecture rather than closed cell [6]. This required some considerations during fabrication of the sandwich panels to minimize resin flow into the core material.

Preliminary compression tests of the foam at 22°C showed results typical of structural foam behavior, with the load on the foam increasing roughly linearly until crushing failure of the cellular structure occurred at approximately 5% strain. The modulus measured, up to the onset of crushing failure, was 23.0 MPa. Unlike conventional structural foams the measured effective modulus at 90°C was 0.18 MPa, up to approximately 10% strain, after which the load for further deformation leveled off. Foam deformed over 20% strain at 90°C was subsequently cooled, locking in the deformed thickness, and then reheated to above the glass transition temperature, where the original foam block thickness fully recovered [7]. These foams have been considered for independent applications; however, it also seems feasible to use the shape memory foam as the core in a structural sandwich panel.

Shape Memory Sandwich Panels

Sandwich panel construction from the shape memory materials is essentially identical to foam core sandwich panel construction based on more conventional wet layup composite constituent materials. The concept of the sandwich panel, and the application, is identical to conventional structural cored panels. By separating the fiber reinforced facesheets with a low density, shear resistant material the moment of inertia is increased and the resulting flexural stiffness is improved. Thus, assuming that the in-plane tensile and compressive properties can be met with a limited number of fiber reinforced plies, great flexural stiffness improvements, at reduced weights, can be realized through the incorporation of sandwich panel technology.

Since the core of a sandwich panel sees primarily shear loading and the facesheets see nearly pure in-plane tension and compression, the application of shape memory resins and foams in sandwich panel construction seems feasible. With the intended heating, the shape memory foam will drop in shear stiffness allowing the facesheets to move

with respect to each other, which results in shape change. The fiber reinforced shape memory resin facesheets also become more flexible, enabling the flexural distortion of the panel. On the tensile surface of the sandwich panel this reduced matrix modulus has no negative effects as the fibers support the forces. However, in the facesheet which is under compression the reduced matrix modulus means that the fibers are less well supported and therefore more prone to local buckling. This local buckling is noted in the deformation of thin shape memory laminates and has been overcome by applying tension while pulling the laminate around a mandrel to accomplish the bending.

Application of tension during bending of foam core sandwich panels was not considered a suitable approach, thus an alternative had to be determined. It was hypothesized that the inclusion of surface plies, on the sandwich panel compression-side, which are cured with a conventional, higher glass transition temperature (T_g) resin as the matrix, would delay local fiber buckling by better supporting the fibers. Further, it was suggested that at elevated temperature the effective neutral axis would shift toward the non-shape memory plies, keeping the majority of the shape memory material in tension. This was successfully demonstrated qualitatively in earlier research [7].

The goal of the current research is to determine the effectiveness of the incorporation of non-shape memory matrix plies into a shape memory sandwich panel in regards to increased deformation, and to better understand the factors limiting the deformation of these structural panels. More specifically, this research investigates the degree of deformation available in shape memory sandwich specimens which are shear constrained to represent locally deformed structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Shape Memory Sandwich Panels

Test specimens were designed using a hybrid matrix approach and a varying fraction of plies on the compression-side which incorporated the non-shape memory resin.

Specimen Preparation

To better understand the potential for recoverable deformation in composite sandwich panels created from shape memory resins, several specimens were fabricated. The sandwich panels were produced by wet layup techniques using the CTD-DP-5.1 shape memory resin, carbon fiber plain weave fabric, and shape memory foam. The foam was sliced to nominally 5.6 mm in thickness and 3 plies of fabric were used for each composite facesheet. The cured facesheet thickness was approximately 0.75 mm, resulting in a total nominal sandwich panel thickness of 7.1 mm.

The focus of this research is to evaluate the effects of a locally deformed sandwich panel rather than a globally heated, and deformed, panel. However, embedding heaters into the laboratory test specimen surface was determined to increase the complexity unnecessarily. The solution arrived at was to use non-deforming inserts at each end of the sandwich test beam, so that no shear would occur in that outer ends even as the temperature increased. These specimens incorporated a non-deforming phenolic core insert at each end and non-shape memory resin to simulate an unheated boundary condition. The sandwich panels were cut into bend beams, nominally 35 mm wide and 250 mm long. Deformed specimens are shown in figure 1 to demonstrate the geometry

and that the specimens using the non-deforming shear inserts do take on a deformed shape consistent with local heating.

Figure 1: (a) global heating, (b) local midspan heating, (c) global heating with phenolic end shear constraints

Figure 1(a) clearly shows the simple deformed shape of a globally heated sandwich beam without end constraints. The foam core has sheared and the facesheets have slid past each other. Midspan thinning is not noted. Conversely, figure 1(b) and (c) show reverse bending and measureable midspan core thinning due to the end-constrained core shear. Figure 1(b) was deformed under local, midspan heating, while the complete specimen of figure 1(c) was heated, but with the shear constrained by the rigid ends.

Specimen Variations

To evaluate the effects of local heating and the effects of the hybrid matrix concept, several specimen configurations were produced. The non-deforming core inserts were a phenolic material commonly used as hardpoints in composites structures. To ensure that the resin bonding to the phenolic would not shear at temperature, all end constrained specimens were created with two wet resins, simultaneously. In this way, all plies in the outer 30mm of each beam were wet out with the non-shape memory 828/3140 system. The remaining roughly 190mm between end constraints used the shape memory resin, except in the non-shape memory compression surface plies under evaluation.

To produce non-shape memory surface plies, 1 and 2 layers of carbon fiber cloth were wet out, cured under vacuum. These pre-cured laminates became the basis for the hybrid laminates, which were produced by wet layup of the two wet resins onto the surface of these pre-cured layers. Completed specimens were postcured to generate the desired glass transition temperatures. Specimens were produced with the midspan region made up of (a) 100% shape memory matrix facesheets, (b) a combination of a 3 ply shape memory matrix facesheet on the tensile surface and a 3 ply compression-side facesheet with the furthest ply from the neutral axis using non-shape memory resin, and (c) a combination of a 3 ply shape memory matrix facesheet of the tensile surface and a 3 ply compression-side facesheet with the 2 plies furthest from the neutral axis using non-shape memory resin. An additional variation was created in which the

sandwich panel used 3 plies of shape memory matrix material on both sides of the shape memory foam core, but included an additional, 4th ply, on the surface of the compression-side.

Experimental Setup

Bend testing was performed in a loadframe environmental chamber, using a 3-point configuration with a large central loading point (50 mm diameter), to reduce the potential for local buckling of the compression-side facesheet, as shown in Figure 2. Phenolic, non-deforming, end constraints were centered over the loading points of the test fixture.

Figure 2: Sandwich Panel Bend Test Fixture

Deformed shapes could be frozen in using the cooling feature of the environmental chamber as needed. The maximum midspan deflection was limited to approximately 41mm by the geometry of the test fixture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stiffness vs. Temperature

Representative sandwich panel bend test results are shown in Figure 3. As measured when testing the shape memory foam, large differences in stiffness are apparent when comparing loading at 22°C to loading at 90°C. At 90°C, well above the glass transition temperature, the mid-span deflection of the shape memory sandwich panel exceeds 25 mm at a force less than 25 N.

Figure 3: (a) Sandwich Panel Test Stiffness at 22°C and 90°C, (b) Deformed Shapes

Photographs of various levels of deformation of a shape memory sandwich panel specimen are shown in figure 3(b). The top image shows the undeformed specimen, with a sequence of two deformed cases shown below. To lock-in the deformed shapes, the environmental chamber and specimen were cooled while the load was maintained. Once the system was well below the deformation temperature the specimen could be removed from the loadframe and examined. The lower case of figure 3(b) shows substantial mid-span deflection where it is clear that the core has measurably thinned in the central region.

Deformation Force

One of the key issues of interest related to the replacement of shape memory resin matrix plies with non-shape memory matrix plies is the effect on the force required to deform the sandwich panel. Temperatures of 56°C and 80°C bracket the quoted 71°C glass transition temperature of the CTD-DP-5.1 shape memory resin. These temperatures were chosen to represent a temperature above the T_g , as well as a temperature which had previously been suggested to result in the highest degree of strain in this shape memory resin [6].

Figure 4 shows the load versus midspan deflection results for 5 specimens. In each case the beam was loaded until the midspan deflection was approximately 12.7 mm. Specimen 3 is 100% shape memory resin matrix, while specimen 4 replaces 1 ply on the compression-side with the non-shape memory matrix, specimen 5 replaces 2 plies, and specimen 6 adds an additional ply with the non-shape memory matrix to the compression-side of the specimen 3 configuration.

Figure 4: Effect of Non-Shape Memory Resin Plies on Deformation Force

The loads required for deformation at 56°C are definitely greater than for the similar specimens tested at 80°C. Comparing geometry 3 at 56°C to 80°C shows a required force of approximately 6N to generate the 12.7 mm deflection at 80°C, while at 56°C almost 17N is required for the same deflection.

Figure 4 also displays the differences, at 80°C, related to the addition of non-shape memory plies. Each of the cases that includes non-shape memory plies requires a

greater deformation force than specimen 3, the all shape memory matrix beam. However, none of these loads are prohibitive. The required load increases as more non-shape memory plies are added to the compressive-side. There is a clear difference between the stiffness of specimens 4 and 5, with specimen 5 requiring about a 10% greater load for a given midspan deflection. Specimen 6 shows the greatest stiffness at 80°C; however, this is expected as the compression-side facesheet is 4 plies thick rather than the 3 plies of all other specimens.

Deformation at Onset of Damage

The primary purpose of adding non-shape memory matrix plies is to overcome early failure due to compression-side facesheet buckling. To determine the midspan deformation at the onset of facesheet buckling, specimens were loaded at the temperature of interest to a predetermined midspan deflection, and then cooled under load, freezing in the deformed shape. This allowed the deformed specimen to be removed from the loadframe for visual inspection. It was not possible to effectively image the midspan region of the compression-side facesheet while under load, as any facesheet buckling occurred under the central loading point. After visual inspection, the specimen was reheated and allowed to return to the original flat condition, and then prepared for reloading.

Upon shape recovery, each specimen was reloaded to an incrementally greater midspan deflection. These steps were repeated at 56°C, as shown in figures 5, 6, to approximately 41 mm, the maximum displacement allowed by the bend fixture. The results for an end-constrained specimen with all shape memory plies, 3HB, are shown in figure 5. Figure 6 shows the corresponding results for the end constrained specimen, 5LB, which replaces 2 of the shape memory plies on the compression-side with 2 plies using the non-shape memory matrix material.

Figure 5: Load versus Midspan Deflection, Shape Memory Resin only - 3HB @ 56C

Comparing the shapes of the load-deflection curves of figure 5, it is clear that the shape begins to change measurably between the loading to 15.2 mm and the loading to 80

17.8 mm. This corresponds to the listing, in Table 1, of the deflection at failure onset for specimen 3HB which is just greater than 15.2 mm. The remaining loading curves of figure 5 show the effects of increasing amounts of compression-side damage. The peak load for each deflection after 15.2 mm shows little change.

The results of figure 6 show that for the comparable specimen with 2 non-shape memory plies, failure is significantly delayed. Each of the loading and unloading curves builds on top of the previous curve, up to the maximum deflection, limited by the bend fixture. Loads to each deflection increase at the limit of each loading cycle. This demonstrates the effectiveness of adding non-shape memory plies to extend the deformation capabilities of these shape memory sandwich panels.

Figure 6: Load versus Midspan Deflection, 2 Non-Shape Memory Plies - 5LB @ 56C

Table 1: Midspan Deflections in (mm) at Onset of Facesheet Failure

Specimen	3 (all SMC)	4 (1 ply non-SMC)	5 (2 plies non-SMC)	6 (1 added ply)
56C	15.4	38.1	40.6	-
80C	12.9	33.0	38.1	20.3

Table 1 summarizes the midspan deflection at onset of damage as determined from the load-deflection plots. It is interesting to note that for each of the sandwich panel configurations represented the deflection is greater at 56°C than at 80°C. This increased strain to failure of this shape memory resin at temperatures below the T_g has been documented previously [6]. However, in these specimens, the underlying reason for the increased midspan deflection at the lower temperature is that the shape memory foam core is better able to support the compression-side facesheet, and thus help resist facesheet failure. Further, at 56°C the non-shape memory plies are further below that T_g and thus, are able to shift the neutral axis further toward the compression side. It is

worth noting that simply adding a non-shape memory ply to the compression surface, as for specimen 6, was not as effective as replacing shape memory plies with non-shape memory plies.

Damage Morphology

At the onset of failure, small visible bumps begin to appear on the raised tows of the woven material, as seen in figure 7(a). As deflection continues beyond the onset of damage, the wrinkles become more apparent along the weave lines as seen in figure 7(b). At later stages, the shape memory core can no longer support the local load of the facesheet and the facesheet buckles into the core as shown in figure 7(c).

Figure 7: Morphology of Damage Progression, Specimen 3 - Shape Memory Resin only

Figure 8: Morphology of Damage Progression, Specimen 4 - 1 Non-Shape Memory Ply

The general form of damage development is the same for the specimens with non-shape memory matrix resin replacing plies on the compression-side of the sandwich panel. However, as shown in figure 8, the additional deflection prior to damage onset is quite appreciable. Figure 8(a) shows the shape of the beam at damage onset, which is more than twice the midspan deflection of the shape memory-only resin matrix specimen shown in figure 7(a).

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research demonstrate the feasibility of applying elastic shape memory composites to sandwich panels. Findings related to the use of a novel hybrid combining fiber reinforced plies of shape memory and non-shape memory resins on the compression-side facesheet suggest that the approach allows much greater deformations to be generated with little effect on the elevated temperature deformation force. Deformation force due to the added non-shape memory plies is found to only increase by 10 – 15%. Allowable bending deflection, prior to local buckling, is nearly tripled using this material modification, independent of tested deformation temperature. Details of failure morphology clearly show that compression-side facesheet buckling is the midspan deflection limiting factor.

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